

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
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**EXPERIENCE IN TREATING INTRA-ARTICULAR FRACTURES OF THE
DISTAL PART OF THE HUMERUS IN CHILDREN**

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ABSTRACT

The treatment results of 95 patients aged 1 to 18 years were analyzed. Depending on the treatment method, the patients were divided into 2 groups. In the main group, closed repositioning and fixation of fractures with spokes through the skin were used to stabilize them, in the control group, closed repositioning and plaster immobilization were performed. A good result was obtained in the main group compared to the control group. Closed reposition with transcutaneous fixation is a method of choice, as it prevents secondary displacement of fragments and contributes to more complete restoration of hand function.

Keywords: fracture, treatment, children, elbow joint, spokes.

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ОТДЕЛА ПЛЕЧЕВОЙ КОСТИ У ДЕТЕЙ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Проанализированы результаты лечения 95 пациентов в возрасте от 1 года до 18 лет. В зависимости от метода лечения больные были разделены на 2 группы. В основной группе применяли закрытую репозицию и фиксацию переломов спицами через кожу с целью их стабилизации, в контрольной группе выполняли закрытую репозицию и гипсовую иммобилизацию. Хороший результат был получен в основной группе по сравнению с контрольной группой. Закрытая репозиция с чрескожным фиксированием является методом выбора, так как предотвращает вторичное смещение фрагментов и способствует более полному восстановлению функции руки.

Ключевые слова: перелом, лечение, дети, локтевой сустав, спица.

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**BOLALARDA YELKA SUYAGI DISTAL QISMI BO'G'IM ICHI SINISHINI
DAVOLASH TAJRIBASI****ANNOTATSIYA**

1 yoshdan 18 yoshgacha bo'lgan 95 nafar bemorning davolanish natijalari tahlil qilingan. Davolash usuliga kura bemorlar 2 guruhga bulib o'rganildi. Asosiy guruh yopiq repozitsiya va siniq bulaklarni barqarorlashtirish maqsadida teri orqali kegaylar bilan mahkamlash usuli qo'llanilgan, nazorat guruhida yopiq repozitsiya va gipsli immobilizatsiya bajarilgan. Nazorat guruhiga nisbatan asosiy guruhda yaxshi natija olingan. Teri orqali mahkamlash bilan yopiq repozitsiya tanlash usuli hisoblanadi, chunki u bo'laklarning ikkilamchi siljishini oldini oladi va qo'l funksiyasini to'liqroq tiklashga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: sinish, davolash, bolalar, tirsak bo'g'imi, kegay.

Dolzarbliqi. Zamonaviy travmatologiyada yosh bolalarda tirsak bo'g'imining sinishi eng dolzarb muammolardan biri hisoblanadi, chunki tirsak bo'g'imining funksiyasi har bir insonning normal ishlashi uchun juda muhimdir. Tirsak bo'g'imida harakatning buzilishi kundalik va kasbiy faoliyatda turli darajadagi qiyinchiliklarga olib keladi [6,9]. Bolalarda tirsak bo'g'imining shikastlanishi tayanch-harakat tizimining umumiy shikastlanishining 40-50% yoki qo'lning barcha sinishlarining 15-20% ni tashkil qiladi [11].

Yelka suyagining distal qismi sinishlarini davolashning ko'plab usullari ishlab chiqilgan [1,4], ular orasida eng keng tarqalgani qo'lni gipsli longeta bilan mahkamlash bilan bir vaqtning o'zida yopiq repozitsiya qilishdir [3,7,10].

Vaholanki, V.N. Merkulova [2] fikriga ko'ra, faqat gipsli bog'lam bilan mahkamlash orqali repozitsiya qilish orqali davolash usulidan voz kechish kerak, chunki ko'p hollarda suyak bo'laklarining ikkilamchi siljishi sodir bo'ladi va bu ko'plab asoratlarga olib keladi deb hisoblaydi. P.Nemsadze [5], bo'g'imlarning deformatsiyalari va kontrakturalari bilan noto'g'ri bitgan sinishlar, bo'laklarning ikkilamchi siljishi kabi asoratlarning oldini olishga qaratilgan asoslangan davolash algoritmining yo'qligi qoniqarsiz natijalarning asosiy sababidir.

Maqsad: Bolalarda yelka suyagi do'nglararo sinishlari va yelka suyagi do'ng boshchasi sinishlarida optimal davolash usulini tanlash.

Material va usullar: Tadqiqotning asosini 2022-2025-yillarda RITOIATMSF Bolalar utkir shikastlanishlari va oqibatlarini bo'limida davolangan 1 yoshdan 18 yoshgacha ($10,3 \pm 0,5$ -yil) bo'lgan 95 nafar yelka suyagi distal qismining bo'g'im ichi sinishlari bo'lgan bemorlarni davolash natijalari tahlili o'tkazildi. Bemorlarni kuzatish muddati kasalxonadan chiqqandan keyin kamida 3 yilni tashkil etdi. Tekshirish usullaridan quyidagi usullaridan foydalanildi:

- rentgenologik - Bauman burchagi, periferik bo'lakning rotatsiya darajasi va boshcha-diafizar burchakning o'zgarishini aniqlash bilan ikki proeksiyada tirsak bo'g'imining standart rentgenografiyasi;

Davolash va natijalari. Davolash jarayonida va uzoq muddatli davrda jarohatlangan tirsak bo'g'imida sog'lom qo'l bilan solishtirganda harakat amplitudasining tiklanishini o'rganish.

Tirsak bo'g'imi sohasida patologiyasi bo'lgan bolalarni davolashning uzoq muddatli natijalarini tahlil qilish tirsak bo'g'imining shakli, funksiyasi: bukish, yozish, rotatsion harakatlar hajmi baholandi; qo'l o'qi klinik va qiyosiy rentgenogrammalarda holati baholandi. Bu davolashning funksional va anatomik natijalarini baholashni (yaxshi, qoniqarli va qoniqarsiz natijalarga ajratgan holda) nazarda tutgan.

O'tkazilgan davolash natijalarini baholashda quyidagi mezonlar qo'llanildi:

1. Yaxshi natija - tirsak bo'g'imidagi harakatlarning to'liq hajmi va 10° gacha varusli deformatsiya.

2. Qoniqarli natija - tirsak bo'g'imida bukuvchi harakatlarning 30° gacha cheklanishi va 20° gacha deformatsiyalanishi.

3. Qoniqarsiz natija - tirsak bo'g'imida bukulishning 30° dan ortiq chegaralanishi, bo'g'imning 30° dan ortiq deformatsiyasi.

Quyidagi davolash usullari qo'llanildi: - yopiq repozitsiya va gipsli immobilizatsiya; - yopiq repozitsiya bilan Kirshner kegaylari yordamida teri orqali mahkamlash.

Ushbu usullar yelka suyagining distal qismi do'nglarining sinib siljishi bilan bo'lgan bemorlarni davolashda qo'llanilgan. Repozitsiya jarohatlangan vaqtdan boshlab 2 kun ichida amalga oshirildi. Repozitsiya paytida distal bo'lakning siljishini bartaraf etishga erishildi. Nazorat guruhida repozitsiyadan so'ng faqat gipsli immobilizatsiya amalga oshirildi, asosiy davolash guruhida esa siniq bo'laklari Kirshner kegaylari bilan mahkamlandi.

Yopiq repozitsiya umumiy og'riqsizlantirish ostida bajarildi, bo'laklar holati kontrol rentgen qilindi. Bo'laklar repozitsiyasi va distal bo'lak siljishi bartaraf etilgandan so'ng nazorat guruhiga gipsli bog'lam qo'yildi, asosiy guruhdagi bemorlarni davolashda esa bo'laklar Kirshner kegaylari bilan teri orqali mahkamlandi.

Teri orqali osteosintez aseptika qoidalariga rioya qilgan holda Kirshner kegaylari bilan amalga oshirildi va quyidagi talablarga rioya qilgan holda bajarildi: barqaror osteosintez uchun periferik va markaziy suyak bo'laklarining kortikal qatlami orqali o'tishi shart bo'lgan 2 tadan 4 tagacha kegaylar ishlatilgan. Asosiy shart – kegay utkaziladigan sohalarda qon tomir-nervlarining joylashuvini hisobga olgan holda va suyak epifizar sohasiga ehtiyotkor bo'lish. Rentgenda suyak qadog'ining bulishi, siniq sohasini bitgandan keyin Kegaylar 3-5 haftada olib tashlandi.

Umuman olganda, 95 nafar yelka suyagi bo'g'im ichi sinishi bo'lgan bemorda qo'llanilgan usulga qarab tirsak bo'g'imida harakatlar hajmi, shuningdek yelka suyagining distal qismiga tegishli rentgenoanatomik ma'lumotlar o'rganildi.

Tadqiqotga kiritish mezonlariga yelka suyagi distal bo'g'im ichi sinishi bo'lgan 95 nafar bemor mos keldi. Asosiy guruhda 51 nafar bemorni tashkil etdi, 44 nafar bemor nazorat guruhiga kiritildi. Asosiy guruhga yelka suyagi bo'g'im ichi do'nglararo sinishi kiritilgan bo'lib, ulardan 41 nafar bemorda yelka suyagi do'nglararo sinishi, 10 nafar bemorda yelka suyagi do'ngligi boshchasi sinishi aniqlangan. Asosiy guruhda yopiq repozitsiyadan so'ng Kirshner kegaylari yordamida bo'laklarning teri orqali stabilizatsiyasi amalga oshirildi. Nazorat guruhida yelka suyagi do'nglararo sinishi bilan 44 nafar bemor, yelka suyagi do'ngligi boshchasi sinishi bilan 28 nafar bemor, yelka suyagi do'ngligi boshchasi sinishi bilan 16 nafar bemor kiritildi. Nazorat guruhdagi bemorlarda yopiq repozitsiya va gipsli immobilizatsiya usulida davolangan. Nazorat guruhida patologiyaning natijasini belgilovchi asosiy omillar teng taqsimlangan, turli xil davolash usullari qo'llanilgan.

Nazorat guruhidagi natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, bilakning sagittal yoki frontal tekislikda normal o'qdan qiyshayishi 35 (80%) bemorda qayd etilgan, ulardan 21 tasida - cubitus varus (shundan normal o'qdan 15° gacha og'ish 10, 20° gacha – 6) 11 bemorda - cubitus rectus 20° dan ortiq, 3 bemorda - cubitus valgus (2 tasida 10° dan ortiq, 1 tasida 15° dan ortiq). Ushbu guruhda bo'laklarning siljishining bo'lishi shishning qaytishi jarayonida ikkilamchi siljish bilan bog'liq.

Nazorat guruhida bo'laklarning bitishi 34 (77,3%) bemorda repozitsiyadan keyingi odatiy muddatlarda bo'lgan. 9 (20,4%) holatda bo'laklarning siljishi va takroriy repozitsiya tufayli bo'laklarning bitishning sekinlashgani qayd etilgan. 1 nafar bemorda do'ng boshchasining soxta bo'g'imi rivojlangan.

Funksional natija: davolanishdan 3 yil o'tgach, harakat amplitudasi shikastlangan tirsak bo'g'imida $-121,7 \pm 1,6$ daraja, sog'lom qo'lda - $152,1 \pm 0,9$ daraja. Defitsit $30,4 \pm 2,0$, $r < 0,001$. Konservativ davolashdan so'ng shikastlangan bo'g'imda tiklangan harakat hajmi 121,7 gradusni tashkil etadi. Ushbu guruhdagi funksional natija qoniqarli.

Asosiy guruhdagi natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, bilakning normal o'qdan qiyshayishi 6 (11,2%) bemorda qayd etilgan: 4 bemorda - cubitus varus (normal o'qdan 10° gacha og'ish 3 bemorda, 15° ga siljish 1 bemorda) birlamchi jarohat tufayli o'sish zonasining buzilishi tufayli, 2 bemorda - cubitus valgus 15° chegarasida.

Funksional natija: davolashdan 3 yil o'tgach, shikastlangan bo'g'imda harakat amplitudasi - $145,6 \pm 1,6$ daraja, sog'lomda qo'lda - $150,7 \pm 0,9$ daraja, defitsit $-5,7 \pm 2,0$, $r < 0,001$. Konservativ davolashdan keyin shikastlangan bo'g'imda tiklangan harakat hajmi $145,6^\circ$ ni tashkil etdi.

Asosiy guruhda anatomik-funksional natijalarning umumiy tavsifi: 48 (95,7%) bemorda yaxshi natija, 3 (4,3%) bemorda qoniqarli natija va qoniqarsiz natija kuzatilmadi. Davolashning erishilgan natijasini baholash bo'yicha bemorlar sonining mutlaq qiymatlari taqsimotini taqqoslaganda, asosiy guruhda nazorat guruhga nisbatan yaxshi va qoniqarli natijalarga ega bo'lgan bemorlarning ustunligi qayd etildi.

Xulosa

1. Olingan ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, do'nglararo sinishlar va yelka suyagi distal qismi do'ng boshchasi sinishlarida bo'laklarni teri orqali barqarorlashtirish bilan yopiq repozitsiya usuli gipsli immobilizatsiya usuliga nisbatan qoniqarsiz natijalar sonini kamaytiradi.

2. Bo'laklarni teri orqali barqarorlashtirish usuli bilan davolash samaradorligini tahlil qilish nisbiy xavf 0 dan 1,01 gacha bo'lganda yelka suyagining distal qismi tomonidan funksional va anatomik buzilishlarning paydo bo'lish xavfini kamaytiradi.

3. Yopiq repozitsiya va gipsli immobilizatsiya bilan solishtirganda stabillashirish maqsadida bo'laklarni teri orqali mahkamlash usulidan foydalangan holda bolalarda yelka suyagi distal qismining do'nglararo sinishlari va do'ng boshchasining sinishlarida yopiq repozitsiya tanlov usuli hisoblanadi, chunki u bo'laklarning ikkilamchi siljishining oldini olish tufayli qo'l funksiyasini to'liqroq tiklashga yordam beradi.

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